

Potentiometric Studies on Complexation Equilibria between some Transition Metal Ions and 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone in Dioxane – Water Medium

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In continuation of our study on the metal complexes of biologically active *o*-hydroxynaphthaldehyde and its derivatives¹, we describe here potentiometric studies on the chelation behaviour of bivalent metal complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde thiosemicarbazone.

Results and Discussion

The values of pK_a (acid dissociation constant) obtained are 10.98, 11.03, 11.17, 11.30 at $I=0.100$, 0.050, 0.025 and 0.010 *M* sodium perchlorate respectively at $20 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

The \bar{n} and pL data were calculated² and analysed using weighted least-squares method³ on a PC-XT computer to get β_n values. The weighted least-squares treatment determines the set of β_n values which makes the function U ,

$$U = \sum_{n=0}^N (y - x - nz) \beta_n x^n$$

nearest to zero by minimising S ,

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^I W_i U^2(x_i, y_i, z_i)$$

with respect to variation in β_n . S_{\min} has the same statistical distribution as χ^2 with K degrees of freedom and the weight defined in accordance with

Sullivan and Rydberg⁴. S_{\min} can be equated to χ^2 . The formation constants of metal chelates thus calculated are summarised in Table 1.

The stability constant order for the bivalent metal chelates of HNATS has been found to be $Mg < Mn < Cd < Pb < Zn < Co < Ni < Cu < UO_2$, which is in good agreement with the order found by Mellor and Maley⁵ and by Irving and Williams⁶. In all the system, the value of $\log K_1$ is greater than $\log K_2$. The $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, $\log \beta_2$ and S_{\min} values at $20 \pm 0.5^\circ$ for the chelates at different ionic strength are given in Table 1. The results show that the stability of metal chelates increases regularly from Mg^{II} to UO_2^{II} , the stability order being independent of the ligand as in many other cases reported earlier. Minor deviation can be predicted on theoretical grounds. The regularity of this sequence can be correlated with monotonic decrease in ionic radii and monotonic increase in the second ionisation potential in passing from Mg^{II} to UO_2^{II} .

For these chelates \bar{n} (average number of ligand species bound to metal ion) values greater than 2.0 have not been obtained. We, therefore, conclude that more than two chelates, i.e. ML and ML_2 chelates are not formed in any of the systems where M and L stand for metal and monodentate ligand species in solution.

The values of proton-ligand stability constants (pK_a) were found to decrease with increase in ionic

strength of the medium which is in agreement with Debye-Hückel equation,

$$pK_a^0 - A \sqrt{\mu} / (1 + \alpha \sqrt{\mu}) + C\mu = pK_a$$

A similar trend has been obtained for the stability of the chelate.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS (NaClO₄) AT 20 ± 0.5° IN 75% (v/v) DIOXANE-WATER MEDIUM

System	Stability constants + S _{min}	Ionic strength (μ)							
		0.100M	0.050M	0.025M	0.010M				
HNATS	pK _a	10.98	11.03	11.17	11.30				
Mg ^{II} -HNATS	log K ₁	3.39	3.35	4.12	4.78				
	log K ₂	3.31	3.23	3.66	3.33				
	S _{min}	0.002 4	0.032 6	0.094 3	0.013 2				
Mn ^{II} -HNATS	log K ₁	5.67	5.75	5.96	6.88				
	log K ₂	4.25	4.20	4.42	4.42				
	S _{min}	0.001 9	0.011 0	0.005 0	0.002 3				
Cd ^{II} -HNATS	log K ₁	6.55	7.01	7.41	7.98				
	log K ₂	4.87	5.05	5.67	5.96				
	S _{min}	0.076 9	0.041 2	0.000 8	0.112 0				
Pb ^{II} -HNATS	log K ₁	7.64	7.88	7.95	8.25				
	log K ₂	5.81	6.03	6.30	6.69				
	S _{min}	0.004 9	0.001 3	0.031 2	0.018 4				
Zn ^{II} -HNATS	log K ₁	8.35	8.54	8.65	8.88				
	log K ₂	6.58	6.75	6.77	6.98				
	S _{min}	0.037 0	0.007 4	0.006 8	0.008 6				
Co ^{II} -HNATS	log K ₁	9.00	9.32	9.37	9.52				
	log K ₂	7.08	7.45	7.67	7.80				
	S _{min}	0.014 9	0.017 5	0.004 2	0.000 0				
Ni ^{II} -HNATS	log K ₁	9.60	9.75	9.85	9.87				
	log K ₂	8.22	8.42	8.52	8.57				
	S _{min}	0.058 0	0.014 9	0.014 9	0.028 0				
Cu ^{II} -HNATS	log K ₁	9.78	9.83	9.88	10.17				
	log K ₂	8.89	8.61	8.78	8.90				
	S _{min}	0.055 8	0.001 7	0.020 5	0.021 4				
UO ₂ ^{II} -HNATS	log K ₁	10.09	10.14	10.30	10.39				
	log K ₂	8.38	9.28	9.28	9.42				
	S _{min}	0.021 7	0.006 6	0.019 2	0.011 1				
Ca ^{II} ions	Mg ^{II}	Mn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Pb ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	UO ₂ ^{II}
log K ₁ ⁰	5.80	6.25	8.25	8.80	9.90	9.80	9.95	10.10	10.55

TABLE 2—E_r (Mn-Zn) AND δH VALUES FOR THE COMPLEXES OF HNATS

Parameters* (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Metal(II) ions				
	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
log K ₁ ⁰	6.25	9.80	9.95	10.10	9.00
ΔG	8.37	13.13	13.33	13.54	12.06
ΔG _R	—	4.76	4.96	5.17	3.69
ΔH _H	—	43.00	62.00	63.00	47.00
ΔH _L	—	47.76	66.96	68.17	50.69
[(n-5)/5]E _r	—	20.17	30.41	40.55	—
δH	—	27.49	36.55	27.62	—

*log K₁⁰ = Thermodynamic stability constant values have been obtained by extrapolating the log K₁ vs μ^{1/2} (straight line) to zero ionic strength. ΔG = Free energy change on complexation, ΔG = 2.303RT log K₁⁰, where R, T and K₁⁰ have their usual significance and at temp. = 293 K. ΔG_R = Change in heat content for the formation of the complex in solution relative to the value of Mn^{II}. ΔH_H = Heat of hydration of metal ions relative to the value of Mn^{II}. ΔH_L = Heat of complexation referred to metal ion in gaseous and ligand in solution state relative to the value of Mn^{II}. n = Number of electrons in 3d-orbital. [(n-5)/5]E_r = Lattice energy difference for Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes. δH = Thermodynamic stabilisation energy.

Thermodynamic stability constants (log K₁⁰) of the complexes have been obtained by extrapolation of the straight line of log K₁ vs √μ to zero ionic strength (Table 2).

Thermodynamic stabilisation energies δ^H and E_r (Mn-Zn) (lattice energy difference for Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes) values have been calculated according to the method of George and McClure⁸. The hydration energies of metal ions (ΔH_H) are those given by George and McClure. The order of enthalpies (ΔH_L) and free energies (ΔG) for the chelate formation have been found to be Mn < Co < Ni < Cu > Zn, whereas the thermodynamic stabilisation energy factor order δ^H is Co < Ni > Cu, which is in agreement with the conclusion reached from ligand field theory.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (HNATS): To 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (HNA) (Aldrich; 1 g) dissolved in the minimum amount of absolute EtOH, was added an aqueous solution of thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (Fluka, A.R.; 0.85 g) in the presence of 2 drops of CH₃COOH, and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h and then cooled overnight in freezer. The product was precipitated by adding dilute HCl and recrystallised from ethanol. The purity of HNATS was checked by m.p., tlc, elemental analysis, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data.

HNATS solution was prepared in freshly distilled 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium. The solutions of the bivalent metal ions, viz. Mg, Mn, Cd, Pb, Zn, Co, Ni, Cu and UO₂ were standardised by EDTA titrations⁹. Tetra-methylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (E. Merck, A.G.) in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium was used as the titrant. Its solution was standardised against oxalic acid.

Perchloric acid (AnalaR) was standardised with Na₂CO₃ and diluted to the required molarity (0.05 M) with conductivity water. Sodium perchlorate (NaClO₄) (E. Merck, A.G.) was used to maintain the ionic strength. 1,4-Dioxane (AnalaR) was purified by the reported method¹⁰. All other solutions were standardised in the usual manner.

An ECIL 5651 pH-meter in conjunction with a glass electrode was used for pH measurements. All measurements were made at definite temperature, by using a MLW (Federal Republic Germany, NBE type) thermostat. A PC-XT computer was used for most of the computation work.

The titrations were performed in a covered double-walled glass cell in an atmosphere of nitrogen, which was presaturated with the solvent (75% v/v, dioxane in water), before passing it through the solution. pH correction was done accordingly¹¹.

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